

DMP Report

058.005 Einführung in das Forschungsdatenmanagement

**Maintenance_True_Usage - Monitoring true usage and
optimizing maintenance**

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1 Abstract

The experiment aims to analyze and optimize the maintenance and usage data of military service vehicles. The primary goal is to derive insights into the patterns of maintenance tasks, costs, and vehicle utilization. The input data consists of three main datasets as input: "Arbeitsaufträge_01012023.csv", "results_Both_14122023.csv", and "Sparepart_14122023.csv". And it contains four csv file and one figure as output: "AnlassTyp_freq.csv", "SP_freq_1st.csv", "SP_freq_2nd.csv", "SP_freq.csv", and "Figure_1_Maintenance.png".

2 Introduction

The primary research question guiding this experiment is how to achieve a realistic and transparent understanding of the usage profiles and maintenance of military logistic vehicles, considering their unique operational contexts and challenges. The objective is to analyse the previous maintenance data for better maintenance planning. To answer this question, the initial step involves collecting data from vehicle control systems, encompassing factors like mileage, maintenance types, and usage history. The raw data should then be pre-processed and then analysed to achieve the objective. Challenges may arise in integrating data from diverse sources, including databases in paper form, to ensure a consistent and transparent capture of vehicle usage. The other challenge is that, as the data comes from the military, it is not possible to make it accessible to everyone. Therefore in this project, datasets are closed access but source codes are open access and are uploaded to the repository. Also instead of input files, empty files with column labels are added to the repository.

3 Eplanation of Experiment

This is a small part of a larger FFG project which a dashboard for maintenance of military service automobiles have been created. Following, this part of the experiment is well described which has three source codes and visually is depicted in Fig 1.

Fig. 1. Architecture of Maintenance TrueUsage project

Dashboard_maintenance.py Python code utilizes the pandas library to preprocess and analyze two datasets related to military service vehicles. It reads data from "Arbeitsaufträge_01012023.csv" and "results_Both_14122023.csv," creating two dataframes, df_AnlassTyp and df, respectively. The code then extracts specific columns ('fahrzeugtyp', 'plate', 'lifetime', 'costs', 'year') from df, forming a new dataframe named new_df. It further manipulates df_AnlassTyp to filter out sub-maintenance tasks, extract the year from the 'Erstell-datum' column, and perform frequency analysis on maintenance types ('AnlassTyp') grouped by Plate Number ('Los/IDMK') and year. The final result is a new dataframe, df_new, presenting the aggregated frequency of three maintenance categories: 'korrektiv,' 'Jahresservice,' and 'präventiv,' for each Plate Number and year combination.

Dashboard_SparePart.py Python code utilizes the pandas library to process two datasets related to vehicle spare parts. It reads data from "Sparepart_14122023.csv" and "results_Both_14122023.csv," creating two dataframes, df and df_fahrzeugtyp, respectively. The code then groups the spare parts data based on the "plate number" ('PNumber') column and calculates the frequency of each spare part for every unique plate number. It adds information about the vehicle type ('fahrzeugtyp') by referencing the 'df_fahrzeugtyp' dataframe. The code exports the resulting dataframe to

"SP_freq_2nd.csv." and "SP_freq_1st.csv" which are different type of cars and "SP_freq.csv," is combination of two types of cars.

The third Python code (MaintenanceFig.py) utilizes the pandas and matplotlib libraries to create a grouped bar chart. It reads data from "AnlassTyp_freq.csv" and extracts the first unique value from the 'Los/IDMK' column. The code then filters the dataframe to include only rows corresponding to this unique 'Los/IDMK' value. Using matplotlib, the code sets up a bar chart with bars representing different maintenance categories ('Jahresservice,' 'korrektiv,' and 'preventiv') for each unique year. The bars are grouped for each year, and their heights correspond to the frequency counts. The resulting chart is labeled and visualizes the maintenance types over the years for the specific 'Los/IDMK.' Finally, the chart is displayed using plt.show().

4 Data management plan

The experiment demonstrates a commitment to fair principles through various aspects of its design and execution. Firstly, the adherence to metadata standards ensures transparency and interpretability of the datasets used. The README files accompanying each dataset provide comprehensive information about the data columns, units, and dataset size. This metadata clarity facilitates reproducibility and understanding, aligning with fair principles.

Moreover, the incorporation of an MIT License underscores the commitment to open science and data sharing. The license outlines usage terms, access restrictions, and attribution requirements, promoting ethical and responsible data handling. Additionally, the provision of a Data Management Plan (DMP) further enhances the fair principles by articulating the strategy for data acquisition, processing, and sharing. The DMP serves as a roadmap for ethical data handling practices, contributing to the experiment's credibility and transparency.

Furthermore, the adoption of three-star CSV files, contributes to the fair principles. By structuring the datasets with clear column headers, using machine-readable formats, and linking related data, these CSV files enhance interoperability and facilitate data integration. This adherence to Linked Data principles fosters a more interconnected and accessible data ecosystem, aligning with the fair principles of Machine actionability, findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.